

Democratic Market Reforms and Economic Liberalization

Fayziyeva N. Sh

*Tashkent State University of Economics, Associate Professors of the
Department of "Economic Theory"*

Abstract: *The economy, being one of the most important spheres of society, is the source of human development. Here people, in order to meet their material and spiritual needs, produce various goods and means, enter into economic relations with each other.*

Keywords: *economy, market, democratic market, liberalization, prices, competition, human activity, free labor, economic life.*

Date of Submission: 20-10-2024

Date of Acceptance: 29-11-2024

Introduction

Under the system of former totalitarian and administrative rule, politics dominated the economy and determined the direction of its development. The economic basis of this system was public property, consisting of state and collective-farm cooperative forms of ownership. The state, owning more than 90% of the production fund, has established a single-power board. As a result, the state centrally managed the economy and economic life on an administrative basis.

Members of the society were deprived of the right to own social property. Entrepreneurship, doing business was prohibited by law. And those engaged in this activity were brought to criminal responsibility as speculators and alien elements

Uzbekistan, which has achieved independence, is implementing fundamental reforms in order to create a democratic, rule-of-law state and civil society based on a socially oriented market economy.

Therefore, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that " The basis of the economy of Uzbekistan, aimed at developing a market economy, is property of various forms. The state, taking into account the legal advantage of consumers, guarantees economic activity, free labor, equality of all forms of ownership, and absolutely equal, in legal terms, protection"

The democratic economic principles inherent in a democratic society are reflected in the following fundamental features of a market economy:

1. Private property;
2. Entrepreneurship and freedom of choice;
3. Personal gain is the main motive of human activity;
4. Competition;
5. A system of free prices;

6. Limiting state intervention in the economy.

The following activities are considered to implement an economically sustainable direction of deepening democratic changes in Uzbekistan and forming the foundations of civil society:

- * liberalizing foreign economic activity and the foreign exchange market, ensuring the free exchange of the national currency for current transactions

- * implementing structural changes in the economy, as well as producing products that can replace imports;

attracting foreign investment to the economy. To do this, create guarantees for the appropriate investment environment and investors

- * direct domestic and external investments to the economy as a whole, including leading areas that ensure the growth of stability of our gold and foreign exchange reserves.

In order to strengthen the processes of liberalization and democratization of economic life, it is advisable to protect the rights of individual and corporate private owners, strengthen their responsibility, and improve the legal framework that ensures freedom of entrepreneurial activity and regulates economic activity. In order to further deepen market reforms and implement the principles of a free economy, the reform of the public administration system will continue.

In order to build a democratic society, a decision will be made to limit the economic activity of the state, to gradually transfer its tasks to governments and self-government bodies, and to introduce the principles of a free economy.

As a final result, a well-formed market economy will be achieved, stable economic growth will be ensured, effective use of economic resources will be achieved, and the population's well-being will increase.

The " Civil Code " of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasizes that property law gives an individual the right to own his own property, at his own discretion and in his own interests, to use and own it, as well as the right to demand the elimination of any violations of his property rights by anyone. The property right is perpetual.

Free enterprise means the conduct of economic, economic activities in a certain area of individuals and their associations, groups for the purpose of making a profit. This also means that entrepreneurs voluntarily enter and exit a particular field.

Freedom of choice expresses the superiority of the rights and interests of consumers, their possession of the freedom to choose goods and services in accordance with their desires, will, tastes, and incomes. People, seeking to get benefits, benefits and profit, use all their abilities.

Competition determines the boundaries of the realization of personal interests of economic entities. In addition, competition encourages manufacturers and sellers to use new equipment and technologies in order to produce ever cheaper, better-quality goods, taking into account the interests, tastes and desires of consumers and buyers.

The role of government and the State in a market economy based on a system of competition and free prices is limited. The State contributes to the management of the market mechanism.

The concept of socio - economic development consists of 3 main parts:

The processes of removing the economy from the state's jurisdiction and its democratization, creating the foundations of a free socially-oriented market economy, are carried out in stages.

At the first stage of the economic reforms carried out in Uzbekistan (1991-1994), we started solving the tasks of eliminating the crisis and stabilizing the economy, as well as forming the foundations of market relations, taking into account the characteristic conditions and characteristics of the republic. For this purpose, the following actions were performed:

- ◆ formation and development of the legal framework for reforms. Adoption of laws aimed at removing property from state ownership and its privatization, on entrepreneurship and a number of laws aimed at forming market relations.
- ◆ creating the foundations of a multi-layered economy through small-scale privatization.
- ◆ preventing a decline in production, ensuring the stability of the financial situation.

At the second stage (1995-1998) of socio – economic reforms in agriculture, the implementation of work on the formation of a new economic system corresponding to market relations began. As a result, the sector of non-state production has developed widely in this industry. We have also developed systems that meet the existing conditions for managing the national economy, its branches and regions.

Conclusion

As the main objective of liberalization, measures are being taken to reduce the control and management functions of the state, and sharply reduce its inappropriate interference in the activities of enterprises.

In the context of economic liberalization, tax incentives are being extended to encourage private business and entrepreneurship, income tax rates are being reduced, and taxation is being simplified.

As a result of the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of freedom of entrepreneurial activity" in 2000, the protection and guarantee of the rights and interests of entrepreneurs has been further strengthened.

The implementation of the processes of economic liberalization in conjunction with the processes of liberalization of the country's political life has strengthened its role in building a democratic state.

REFERENCES:

1. Rakutina N. M. Modern problems of Russian small business. projects. - 2010. - No. 12. - pp. 83-90.
2. Semenov B.C., Kaminsky I. M., Kaminsky N. A. Hotel management: a reference guide]. Popova, Moscow: Business Center Publ., 2009, 412 p.
3. Kosarikov A., Sokolova O. Small Business in Russia: Development Programming/ / Problems of management theory and practice. - 2012.-№ 10. pp. 158-163.
4. Khizrich R., Peters M. Entrepreneurship, or how to start your own business and achieve success: Issue 1. Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship : Pres. From English. - M.,: Progress, 1990-P. 193.
5. Semenov B.C. справочное, Kaminsky I. M. Hotel management: a practical guide. N. A. Popova, Moscow: Business Center Publ., 2009, 412 p.